

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SOME SPECIES AND FORMS OF THE TASHKENT BOTANICAL GARDEN (UZBEKISTAN), RECOMMENDED FOR USE IN VERTICAL GARDENING

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Abstract

The article provides data on some promising species of the Tashkent Botanical Garden recommended for vertical gardening.

Keywords: vertical gardening, assortment, landscape design, perspective, decorative, Tashkent Botanical Garden, Uzbekistan.

The importance of decorative trees in ensuring environmental sustainability, as well as greening settlements, is highly appreciated in the world. Today, one of the main problems in urban planning is the organization of landscaping on a scientific basis. Currently, the global warming process is being observed all over the world. This, in turn, has an impact on the ecological environment.

Landscaping of settlements – cities, districts, villages – is one of the main means of landscaping these places. Special attention is paid in the resolutions of the President and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the improvement of settlements. The expansion of the range of decorative species of trees and shrubs used in landscaping, the search for varieties and forms that can adapt to the conditions of our country, the introduction of scientifically based technology care are topical issues of today.

It is known that trees and shrubs absorb carbon dioxide from the air and enrich the air with oxygen. 1 ha of green spaces absorbs 8 kg of carbon dioxide from the air in an hour. The same amount of carbon dioxide is released by 200 human lungs when breathing. In other words, the moderate air content required for breathing of 1 person in the city is provided by green spaces with an area of 50 m². But most of the carbon dioxide is dispersed in the atmosphere, and only a small part is absorbed by green spaces.

As is known, in nurseries specializing in the breeding and cultivation of ornamental species of trees and shrubs, it is relevant to study the bioecological features of promising plants, study the factors affecting their growth and development, as well as improve various breeding methods for landscaping. Most of the assortment currently used in the field of landscaping in our republic consists of introduced shrubs. Climbing plants are of particular importance in the landscaping of settlements. Their importance is invaluable, especially in newly constructed buildings, as newly planted trees and shrubs will not yet grow and develop well. During the period when the construction was completed, the use of climbing plants to create a green landscape is the main tool of landscape design. The expansion of human settlements in the world requires the widespread introduction of landscape design and landscaping in accordance

with the traditions of modern urban planning. Decorative species of trees and shrubs that are biologically resistant to urban conditions are of particular importance here, the determination of their resistance to environmental factors, the assessment of decorative properties and the development of reproduction methods in various conditions are of great scientific and practical importance.

Rooftop landscaping is very popular in Europe. The green and flower-covered roofs are very beautiful and emphasize the aesthetics of the building. Green roofs improve thermal insulation, reduce dustiness of the air, increase the noise protection of the room, protect the roof from ultraviolet rays, and purify rainwater, so that pollution and soil erosion are not observed. Vertical landscaping, in harmony with the walls of the fence, as well as with the walls of houses and balconies, gives the rooms beauty and grace. Climbing plants decorate the entrances to buildings, making them decorative and cozy. With the skillful use of green plants in the vertical landscaping of walls and corners of the building, their architectural appearance becomes more expressive. Climbing plants are also of great importance when hiding inconspicuous side parts of buildings. However, excessive vegetation can lead to clogging of architectural parts of the building. Green plants should not cover the brick, ceramic texture. Only in places with high solar radiation, the walls of buildings can be completely covered with green climbing plants. This method is most often used in hospitals and sanatoriums. Climbing plants are also more often used in the design of small and large verandas.

The following plants are used in vertical gardening: wild grapes of different varieties (vines), Amur vine, clematis, honeysuckle, actinidia, kirkazon (aristolochia), ivy, lemongrass, etc.; when landscaping balconies and verandas, from annual, climbing plants – nasturtiums, ipomoea, Japanese hops, Gourd (Bottle gourd), sweet peas and beans. But the full-fledged decorative appearance of these plants manifests itself in the middle of summer or autumn. For landscaping verandas and pergolas, it is recommended to use the following plants: from woody stems – grapevine (grapes), moonseed, clematis (clematis), honeysuckle-caprifol, aristolochia, climbing roses and climbing hydrangea; from herbaceous – hops, gladiantha (*Thladiantha*), bryonia

(*Bryonia*); from annual – ipomoea, Turkish pods, sweet peas.

The assortment for landscaping roofs should be chosen carefully, they should be light-loving, wind-resistant, adapt well to new living conditions, have a small root system, be drought- and frost-resistant. Vertical landscaping helps to make the walls of buildings aesthetically attractive in a short time, to create dense and beautiful panels. Lianas, ferns, mosses, perennial mountain plants are used for landscaping walls, which are unpretentious, adapt well to life on vertical surfaces and help to quickly cover the surface of the wall. Vertical plant curtains help to reduce the temperature of the wall surface, increase biodiversity, protect from noise and dust, have a positive effect on the psychological state of a person, and allow you to decorate the styles

of rooms. Vertical landscape design in a modern interpretation was invented by Stanley Hart White at the American University in Urbana-Champaign, Illinois, between 1931 and 1938. Modern vertical gardening has a number of advantages: with a total large area of green mass, it does not take up much space, creates a good mood, allow you to relax, relieve stress. We can use several types of plants at once. Plants growing in a vertical plane actively absorb carbon dioxide and saturate the air with oxygen. A room with a vertical living wall creates a unique microclimate, reminiscent of the atmosphere of a real garden. Vertical gardening can be arranged in a specific place or room using simple plants such as moss. Moss forms a real green wall. The table below shows the species and forms available in the Tashkent Botanical Garden, recommended for use in vertical gardening (table).

Table

Species and forms of the Tashkent Botanical Garden recommended for use in vertical gardening

1	Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia</i>	<i>durior</i> Hill
2		<i>Aristolochia</i>	<i>tomentosa</i> Sims
3		<i>Aristolochia</i>	<i>clematitis</i> L.
4	Ranunculaceae	<i>Clematis</i>	<i>virginiana</i> L.
5		<i>Clematis</i>	<i>orientalis</i> L.
6		<i>Clematis</i>	<i>tangutica</i> Maxim. Korsh.
7		<i>Clematis</i>	<i>songarica</i> Bunge
8		<i>Clematis</i>	<i>serratifolia</i> Rehder
9		<i>Clematis</i>	<i>flammula</i> L.
10		<i>Clematis</i>	<i>vitalba</i> L.
11		<i>Clematis</i>	<i>viticella</i> L.
12		<i>Clematis</i>	<i>paniculata</i> J.F. Gmel.
13	Araliaceae	<i>Hedera</i>	<i>colchica</i> (K. Koch)
14		<i>Hedera</i>	<i>helix</i> L.
15		<i>Hedera</i>	<i>pastuchovii</i> Woronow
16		<i>Hedera</i>	<i>helix</i> var. "Esther"
17			<i>helix</i> var. "gloire de Marengo"
18			<i>helix</i> var. "Goldchild"
19			<i>helix</i> var. "tricolor"
20	Apocynaceae	<i>Periploca</i>	<i>graeca</i> L.
21		<i>Vinca</i>	<i>herbacea</i> Waldst. & Kit.
22			<i>major</i> L.
23			<i>minor</i> L.
24		<i>Apocynum</i>	<i>lancifolium</i> Russ.
25		<i>Apocynum</i>	<i>scabrum</i> Russ.
26		<i>Trachelospermum</i>	<i>jasminoides</i> (Lindl.) Lem.
27	Bignoniaceae	<i>Campsis</i>	<i>radicans</i> (L.) Bureau
28			<i>grandiflora</i> (Thunb.) K.Schum.
29		<i>Bignonia</i>	<i>capreolata</i> L.
30			<i>unguis-cati</i> L.
31	Fabaceae	<i>Wisteria</i>	<i>chinensis</i> (Sims) DC.
32		<i>Clematis</i>	<i>vitalba</i> L.
33	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Lonicera</i>	<i>caprifolium</i> L.
34			<i>x brownii</i> (Regel) Carriere

***Hedera helix* L.** – Common ivy, European ivy is a species of flowering plants in the Araliaceae family. It is widespread in some parts of Europe and Western Asia. It is popular as an evergreen ornamental plant growing on tree trunks, walls and hedges of gardens. It grows up to 20-30 m in height, also known as a species

that covers the ground where there are no tree trunks, rocks, rotting walls or vertical surfaces. It is raised with the help of aerial roots with "pads" tightly adjacent to the substrate. As a rule, it grows best in areas with a large range of soil pH (ideal pH = 6.5), preferring moist shady places and avoiding direct sunlight, which can

cause drying in winter [1]. The leaves are alternate, 50-100 mm long, the leaf petiole is 15-20 mm; they come in two types: young leaves with five palmate lobes on creeping and climbing stems and large heart-shaped

leaves on profusely flowering stems open to full sunlight, usually grows in the crowns of trees to the tops of high cliffs (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – General view of the growth of *Hedera helix L.*

The flowers bloom from late summer to late autumn, small, 3-5 cm in diameter in umbellate inflorescences, greenish-yellow, very rich in nectar, which are an important food source for bees and other insects in late autumn. Fruits with a diameter of 6-8 mm, from purplish-black to orange-yellow, ripen in late winter [2] and are an important food source for many birds. Each berry contains from one to five seeds, which spread after being eaten by birds. In Europe, it is often planted to cover walls, and the Bavarian government recommends growing it in buildings because of its ability to cool the interior in summer, provide insulation in winter, and protect the interior from soil moisture and temperature [3-5].

Humulus lupulus L. – Common hops are from the family Cannabaceae, a perennial vine of the genus *Humulus L.* The stem is curly clockwise, four-sided, hollow, covered with sharp thorns, up to 7 m long. The rhizome is long, creeping. The leaves are three- to five-

lobed, heart-shaped, ovate with sharp edges, large-filiculated at the edges, opposite, long-stemmed, with internodes; the upper leaves are whole. They are dioecious. The male inflorescences on the branches of the second order consist of dichasias, which turn into whorls. The male flowers are small, green, and consist of a five-petaled inflorescence and five erect filamentous stamens. Inside the complex oval-shaped inflorescences are female flowers. The staminate flowers arranged in pairs are racemose inflorescences of underdeveloped leaves with folds of two to four to six flowers in the axils without flowers of the first order. The lupulysts fuse with the fruit and consist of yellow glands containing lupulin. Female flowers consist of an achene, membranous at the base, surrounded by a whole cup-shaped inflorescence at the edges. It blooms in July and August. The nut fruit, consisting of a spirally coiled whorl, ripens in August-September (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – General view of the growth of *Humulus lupulus* L. in the Tashkent Botanical Garden

The plant is widespread in the temperate climates of Eurasia and North America; it is also found in northern Africa (in Morocco). The plant's homeland is unknown. In Russia, it is widespread almost everywhere, except in the Far North, the Caucasus and Altai, in the European part and Western Siberia. It grows along riverbanks and in deciduous forests, in shrub forests, on willow and alder soils. It has long been grown on special plantations. Hop fruits contain essential oil (up to 3%), hop resins, wax, bitter substances (16-26%, according to other sources 11-21%), valerian, hop acids, glycoside lupulin, carotene, ascorbic acid, choline, thiamine, nicotinic acid, yellow dyes, tannins, contains tannins (3%), flavonoids. Young branches and leaves contain 0.095-0.19% ascorbic acid. The essential oil of hops is fragrant, light or orange in color, the main component of which is myrcene (30-50%) and myrcenol. Hop resins are a complex complex of substances (a mixture of phenols, tar acids and neutral resins). The quantitative composition of phenols and resin acids determines the brewing value of a particular hop variety. The composition of bitter substances varies depending on the hop variety and growing conditions (climate and soil), as well as on the time of harvest. The fruits of hops, which used to be called “hooters”, were used for dyeing fabrics. Bees collect pollen from hops. An ornamental, climbing, creeping plant is grown to decorate hedges and balconies. Long stems can be used to produce fiber suitable for making coarse burlap and ropes [6].

The fruits of hops harvested at the beginning of maturation have long been used in brewing and baking (for the production of liquid yeast), in baking some types of bread. Hop tannins regulate fermentation and prevent beer fermentation. Essential oil, resin, and lupulin give beer its characteristic aroma and bitter taste

[6]. Newly emerged young branches of hops are eaten in spring in vegetable dishes such as asparagus or cauliflower, and as nettles for green cabbage soup [7]. Hops are a moisture-loving and heat-loving plant. The sum of temperatures for its development averages 2,600 °C. The optimal average daily temperature is 16-18 °C. The optimal annual precipitation is 450-650 mm; relative humidity is 70-80%. Ordinary hops are demanding on the type of soil. It develops well on fertile soils with a slightly acidic reaction. Chernozems, gray forest, light and loamy soils are best suited. Sandy, carbonate and swampy soils are unsuitable. It absorbs 3.5-4 times more nutrients (NPK) from the soil than winter wheat. It is considered a plant sensitive to zinc deficiency in the soil [8]. Information about the biochemical composition of *Humulus lupulus*, its role in the pharmaceutical industry, and its medicinal properties can be found in many foreign literatures [9-14].

***Lonicera caprifolium* L.** – a liana of the Caprifoliaceae family, reaching 6 m in height, growing mainly in temperate regions. Homeland – Central and South-eastern Europe, the Caucasus. Distribution: Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Czechoslovakia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, North Caucasus, Romania, Turkey, Yugoslavia. Introduced: Belgium, Dominican Republic, France, Great Britain, Haiti, Ireland, Crimea, Michigan, New Jersey, New York, Norway, Nova Scotia, Ontario, Poland, South European part of Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Uzbekistan [15]. The young branches are light green, sometimes purple, and the bark is brown on the old branches. The leaves are opposite, broadly elliptical, 4-10 cm long, dark green above, gray below. The flowers are yellowish-white, often reddish on the outside, collected in the axils of leaves fused at the top. The corolla is 4-5 cm long, double-edged. The flowers are fragrant, mostly late, and fragrant. The flowering

period is from May to July. The fruits are inedible, orange or red in color, 6-8 mm in diameter; do not fuse with each other. The fruit is short, so the fruits look as

if they are "glued" to the leaf. It ripens in late July-August (Fig. 3).

Figure 3 – *Lonicera caprifolium* L. during the flowering period

Lonicera caprifolium is often used in vertical gardening as a promising decorative garden plant. It is very unpretentious, grows quickly and is well resistant to formative pruning. *Caprifol* is light-loving, demanding of soil fertility and moisture. It is propagated by seeds, cuttings, but it is very easily propagated by root layering. *Caprifol* flower extract is used in the perfume industry and aromatherapy [16].

Thus, vertical gardening in landscape design is a popular trend today. It has both aesthetic and practical significance. A hedge of climbing plants can be used to create so-called green rooms. For this purpose, fences, screens in the form of lattices made of wood, plastic nets, weaves made of willow and walnut rods are supported.

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